

FRENCH LITERATURE OF THE ROMANTIC ERA

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Annotation.

This article is about the literature of the French romantic period, which represents the scene of the French bourgeois world of the XIX century. This article concerns le mouvement réaliste et les écrivains réalistes français.

Key words:

Romanticism, romantics, realism, realism stream, realist writers, "Romantic aesthetics".

The XIX century was a turning point in the development of French literature. First, the literacy level of the entire population increased, and literary works became available to the general public. Secondly, a number of socio-economic upheavals occurred in the life of the country, which could not but affect the worldview of writers and the nature of literature in general. At this time, the works are not instructive, but appeal to the human mind, encouraging him to personal and spiritual growth. After the events of the French Revolution, writers began to appeal to the general public, art became more democratic, heroes and the brightest types emerged from the people, works became more alive.

One of the most common currents in literature is romanticism. The century, conditionally called the XIX century, was a new era in world history and literature. "The word romanticism (romantic spirit) was adopted in Germany, and the sources of romantic poetry are seen by the Germans in the poetry of the troubadours born in the era of Christianity and chivalry ... Sometimes, the Germans use the word classic as a synonym for the perfect o They use it."¹

Romanticism became a reflection of the new consciousness of the peoples; the search for literary forms, the return to folk art, made it possible to formulate questions that are relevant for European civilization to this day. At the turn of the XVIII-XIX centuries, a stage of romanticism appeared in the culture of Europe, including America, which was completely different from the period of thinking and philosophy of the Enlightenment period. Romanticism, which gradually entered the culture and art of England, France, Russia and other European countries from Germany, enriched the artistic world with new colors and stories. The name of the new movement was born from the close connection of several meanings of monophonic words from different countries - romanticisme (France), romance (Spain), romantic (England). Later, the name of the movement took root and has remained as a romance to this day.

¹ Жермена де Сталь. О Германии. О влиянии страстей на счастье людей и народов. // Литературные манифесты западноевропейских романтиков. -М.: 1980, -с.384.

“Le mot réalisme apparaît pour la première fois en France dans un article anonyme du *Mercure* du XIX^e siècle en 1826. C’est un magazine littéraire qui critiquait et s’opposait aux idées du romantisme surtout dans l’art, et plus précisément la peinture. Ce terme a été bien mentionné par Emile Lettré, philosophe et lexicographe, dans son *Dictionnaire de la langue française* où on voit que le terme est appliqué aux beaux-arts comme à la littérature. Enfin et grâce à l’utilisation bien remarquée du terme réalisme par les écrivains et les peintres, le mot entre dans le *Dictionnaire de l’Académie française* en 1878”². That is, the word realism appears for the first time in France in the XIX century in an anonymous article published in *Mercure* in 1826. It was a literary magazine that criticized and opposed the ideas of Romanticism, especially in art, more specifically in painting. The term is well mentioned by the philosopher and lexicographer Emile Lettre in his *Dictionary of the French Language*, and we see the term applied to the visual arts and literature. Finally, thanks to the good use of the term realism by writers and artists, this word entered the vocabulary of the French Academy in 1878. Romanticism got tired of bourgeois reality and ran away from it to the world of ideas, hopes (ideal), bright dreams. However, the contradictions of the bourgeois system began to surface more and more, and life did not improve as expected. Under these conditions, it was necessary to find out what is wrong with that bourgeois reality, its vices and contradictions, in order to improve life. Because, as mentioned, now people are forced to look at their marriages and relationships with healthy eyes. This created the need to depict the existence truthfully and truthfully. As a result, realism appeared³. Realists, like romantics, do not depict dreams, but life itself, existence, with all its contradictions and complexity. So, truthfulness is the first and main requirement of realism. However, honesty alone is not enough. Because realism does not describe everything that happens in life, all the visible things. In addition to the truthfulness of details, realism also requires the truthfulness of typical characters acting in typical circumstances. So, realism does not only give the details of images, characters, and events, but on the contrary, it sorts them, summarizes them, and typifies them⁴. By reading the works of the Romantic period, one can get an idea of the French society of this period. For example, V. Hugo (“*Les Misérables*”, “*Les travailleurs de la mer*”, G. Flaubert (“*Madame Bovary*”), Guy de Maupassant (“*Bel-Ami*”, “*Une Vie*”) describe the real and true life of French society.

It is necessary to refer to the philosophical and literary-theoretical views of the creators of this trend, to study the works they created, in the study of the flow of romanticism, which had a great influence on the development of world literature, and the fiction belonging to this flow. The famous German philosopher and literary critic Jean Paul Richter, August and Friedrich Schlegellar and Clemens Brentano, Goethe, Schiller, F. Klinger, H. Heine, Byron and Shelley in England, F. Chateaubriand, Germaine de Stal, S. Node, V. Hugo in France , J. Sand, Eugène Sue, A. de Mousse, G. Flaubert and Guy de Maupassant are major representatives of European romanticism. The founders of European romanticism had a deep philosophical self-awareness, and the concept of romanticism literature was born.

² <http://www.larousse.fr/encyclopedie/nom-commun-nom/r%C3%A9alisme/86007> (2012-03-07)

³ "ADABIYOTShUNOSLIK ASOSLARI"-Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti, K.Qurambayev 82-b.

⁴ "ADABIYOTShUNOSLIK ASOSLARI"-Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti, K.Qurambayev 82-b.

Incomparable works created by representatives of the literary movement of the Romantic era - German poets, poetry of Goethe, Schiller, Heine, tales of Novalis, Ludwig Thicke, Ernest-Amadeus Hoffmann, poems of Byron and Shelley, representatives of English romanticism, historical novels of W. Scott, representatives of French romanticism literature. Poems, novels of W. Hugo, Charles Nodding, Alfred de Musset, George Sand, A. Dumas, Eugène Sue, Stendhal, P. Mérimée. The novels and short stories of G. Flaubert and Guy de Maupassant are masterpieces of world classic literature.

Regarding the novels written in the Romantic period, the French writer Stendhal wrote: "Un roman est un miroir qui se promène sur une grand-route. Tantôt il reflète à vos yeux l'azur des cieux, tantôt la fange des borbiers de la route. Et l'homme qui porte le miroir dans sa hotte sera par vous accusé d'être immoral ! Son miroir montre la fange, et vous accusez le miroir ! Accusez bien plutôt le grand chemin où est le borbier, et plus encore l'inspecteur des routes qui laisse l'eau croupir et le borbier se former"⁵. Meaning - "A novel is a mirror on the highway. Sometimes it reflects the glow of the sky to your eyes, sometimes it reflects the swamp of the road. And the person who carries a mirror in his cap will be accused of being dirty by you! Its mirror shows dirt and you blame the mirror! Instead, blame the swampy highway and even more so the highway inspector for allowing the water to stagnate and create the swamp".

The famous art historian V. V. Vanslov in his book "Aesthetics of Romanticism" states that the artists belonging to this movement (composer, painter, dramatist, genre, philosophers) that emerged in world literature and art are the owners of rare talents who have made a great contribution to the spiritual and spiritual development of humanity, and in their work, the dreams and ideals of all humanity are embodied. says that it is reflected brightly. "Romantics are strangers to selfish interests and evil; the appreciation of beautiful, pure-hearted, compassionate people, the harmony of man and the world (that is, the harmony of people with the beauty of the world), a free and happy life, heroic deeds for the happiness of mankind, the unity and brotherhood of highly spiritual, enlightened people, the realization of all the abilities of talented people they wish to come out. In reality, romantics see the opposite, misery, slavery, need, depravity and corruption, the decay of the individual (humanity)⁶.

The worldview of a person, imbued with the spirit of romanticism, the romantic character is closely related to the concepts of grandeur, nobility, virtue, conscience, different from the cold rationalism, sometimes distant from real life, sometimes too much pleasure. may be full of excitement or endless sadness. But it is always a striving for some kind of spiritual and moral ideal. So, romanticism means hope, aesthetic ideal, deep thought, passionate passion, struggle and rebellion against evil.⁷

The author of the monograph "Esthetics of Romanticism", V. V. Vanslov, quotes the opinion of German romanticism from the work "Aesthetics" of the famous German philosopher G. Hegel: "Poets such as F. Schiller express their deep sadness about the failure of noble ideals in sincere, moving words (also in their works).) represents". G. Hegel criticizes

⁵ Stendhal, Le Rouge et le noir, 1830 La Bibliothèque électronique du Québec Collection À tous les vents Volume 776 : version 1.0 p.97

⁶ В.В.Ванслов. эстетика романтизма. «Искусство», М. 1966, стр. 4-5

⁷ Қаршибаева У.Д. Француз романтизм прозасининг поэтик хусусиятлари (Шатобриан ва В.Гюго ижоди мисолида). Дисс... филология фан.доктори. – Тошкент, 2016. – В. 20

romantic artists as subjective idealists. However, in our opinion, the romantic artists themselves explain the aesthetics of romanticism better, deeper and clearer than G. Hegel. In this sense, V. Vanslov cites the opinions of several romantics about the relationship between reality and ideal. "Aesthetics of Romanticism" began to appear in works written in various genres, in the form of prefaces, letters, reviews, and diaries in the process of solving creative tasks. The theory of romanticism was formed very freely in such works without any order or system⁸.

Realistic elements are present in the creations of all periods. Realism (Latin *realis* - material) - portrays the reality of life in accordance with the original, requires truthfulness of details and images. Loyalty to the truth of life is its main motto. Realists paid special attention to the vitality of images and events. All elements such as the language of the work, the speech of the hero, the subject, and the conflict are subject to the requirement of authenticity. This method allows the creator to tell the truth about the reality and people around him, to see the truth about reality and people by embodying real life and real people in the eyes of the reader. 'allows display. The services of the great figures of realistic literature as truth fighters are incomparable⁹. Realists showed people in the vortex of everyday problems, and as a result, they tried to study human feelings, character, and nature.

In conclusion, it can be said that every work created by French writers during the romantic period gave the reader the opportunity to imagine the past, present and future of each character, because the events of the work are related to each other in a historical sequence and are realistic. is distinguished by The literature of this period was distinguished by a deep and truthful description of negative events in life. It is based on the ideas of patriotism and patriotism, from the position of these progressive ideas, it evaluates the events of life, and the problems of life that hindered the interests of the working people, the development of social life, the struggles for a fair life, and the aspirations on this path. sharply condemns them, exposes them. In the works of the writers of the XIX century romantic period, the closeness of realism to life and the people increased even more, and its tools became even more perfect

⁸ В.В.Ванслов. эстетика романтизма. «Искусство», М. 1966, стр. 6.

⁹ Қаямов О. Чет эл адабиёти тарихи. Т., 1979.

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